

INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL FACTORS ON VOCATIONAL CAREER CHOICES IN TECHNICAL INSTITUTIONS IN KENYA - A SURVEY OF CATHOLIC PRIVATE INSTITUTIONS IN NAKURU DIOCESE

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to investigate influence of social factors on vocational career choices of students in Catholic-sponsored technical institutions located in the Catholic Diocese of Nakuru, Kenya. The study was guided by the research question: What is the influence of social factors on vocational career choices in the aforementioned institutions? The study was grounded on Krumboltz theory of social learning. The empirical literature covered various societal factors. A Convergent parallel mixed method design was used whereby 292 respondents participated in the study. Purposive, stratified and simple random sampling techniques were applied in sampling of institutions, administrators, teachers and students respectively. For data collection, interview guides were used for teachers and principals while questionnaires were employed to facilitate data collection from students. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences programme was used to aid analysis of quantitative data from the students while qualitative data from teachers and principals were organized into themes. Analysis of both qualitative and quantitative data were done independently then mixed at the end during interpretation. The study revealed that 91.6% of students are influenced by immediate people they interact with. It was also found that 55.6% never had prior working experience. The study revealed that as family and friends influence students in technical and vocational training institutions there is still a large number (49.3%) who make choices according to their own personal interest. Majority of

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the students (61.8%) perceived the courses they were pursuing as being very difficult but also marketable. Electrical installation was found to have the highest number of enrollment for national examinations followed by mechanics. The study recommended to Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development to introduce subjects at high school level that could expose students to vocational careers. It was further recommended that technical institutions should come up with guiding policies on how to help and streamline student's choices on vocational careers.

Keywords: Catholic Diocese of Nakuru, social factors, technical institutions, vocational career choices

1. Introduction

Unemployment is becoming an issue of major concern in our daily life especially with increased yearly output of graduates from our tertiary institutions and universities. One way to curb this problem is to expand more areas that can create employment opportunities such as training more in vocational careers which offer skills. During the last 70th session of the United Nation summit on Sustainable Development Goals (UNESCO, 2015), ending of global economic poverty was highlighted and creation of employment to all youths suggested as one of the key solutions. In addition, one of the means to create more employment was identified through promoting vocational technical training at all levels (UNESCO, 2015) This was the only way to assure the youths' possibility of both employment and self-employment depending on the skill learnt is guaranteed.

In other parts of the world, vocational training is also viewed as the best alternative to curb the problem of unemployment among the youths despite challenges youths face in choosing different vocational careers. The biggest challenge relative to vocational training systems in Vietnam was found to be progress from secondary level to tertiary level. There were lessons that are more theoretical in secondary level on technical vocation training which disadvantaged the students when they joined technical institutions. The Vietnam government had to change this system of technical education approach and make it more practical at secondary level in order to promote more students to take vocational training at tertiary level.

In Europe, the situation is different according to TVET (Technical and vocational education training) and skill development report by European Union (EU, 2012). In this report, the main focus for TVET training is for promotion of job creation, decent work, rights at work and social protection. From the report, European TVET programs are the

most well- funded than any other regions followed by Asia, central Asia and the Pacific. One main success from the report in Europe is the realization of how globalization is changing the face of TVET programs due to the ever- changing technology in the industrial sector. Furthermore, the idea of EU member states adopting the idea of supporting quality TVET and skills education has encouraged the youths not to shy away from choosing vocational careers.

African governments need to put a lot of efforts in funding TVET program in order to promote vocational training right from high schools to tertiary institutions. Mensah, Mettle & Ayima (2014) did a study in Ghana and focused on factors that influence career choices in vocational courses. They stressed that governments should encourage vocational training because they give youth opportunities to get employable skills thus reducing economic poverty and changing attitudes towards vocational occupation. Unfortunately, most high schools focus on making students to qualify for university entries and give less attention to vocational oriented subjects hence, creating an attitude that vocational courses are second in terms of priority.

The Kenya's report for the 2014 Ministerial Conference for Youth employment dwelt very much on how to improve vocational skills among the youths (Kaane, 2014). One of the most important finding cited was the mismatch of vocational courses taken by the youth in our technical training verses the industrial skill demand on the labour market. On the same note, Kenya Association of Technical Training Institutions, (KATTI, 2015) stresses that investing in TVET (Technical and Vocational Education Training) education equips learners with skills and competence that are relevant to the world of work today. Table 1 as adapted from Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS) shows how government investment on TVET education has been reducing from the year 2011 to 2016 contrary to what KATTI (2015) report suggest. The table clearly shows an increase on ministerial expenditure in other levels like primary, secondary, university and Higher Education leaving technical education on the lower side.

According to World Bank (World Bank, 2004) report on strengthening the foundation of education and training in Kenya, vocational training was recognized to offer parallel opportunities either as alternatives to the general education or as after school training. The report clarified vocational institutions as starting from youth polytechnic offering artisan and craft courses, then progressing to middle level colleges offering certificates and diplomas and finally where possible university education. In order for successful vocational training to take place effectively, vocational career guidance has to be done in order to guide learners on choosing the right career path. An investigation into this problem was to be done in order to identify and recommend how

the influencing factors can be dealt with by administrators in order to assist learners in technical institutions make the correct choices in their career selection.

There is a great need to boost enrolment and effectiveness of training through better student training match in both public and private institutions. According to Hicks, Mbiti and Miguel (2011) in their work on vocational education voucher delivery and labour market returns, public vocational training institutions tend to focus more on traditional skills like constructions, mechanics, tailoring and plumbing among others; while private institutions, are narrower in scope but allow students to specialize in specific skills like computer software. In Nakuru, technical institutions have tried to address these needs by offering practical courses such as motor-vehicle mechanics, plumbing, electrical engineering, painting, tailoring and dress making among others; especially in Catholic sponsored institutions. The Catholic Church is trying very much at its capacity to respond to the needs of the society especially in this area of promoting vocational training among the youths.

Whether public or private vocational careers need to be promoted as once students are trained in either institution, they contribute towards meeting one of the sustainable development goals. That is eradication of poverty through promotion of skills which will lead to either self-employment or becoming employed.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

According to Kenya National Bureau of Statistics, unemployment rate had reached 40 percent in Kenya by December 2011, thus leading to social- economic problems in the society. This situation needs great and immediate attention. From the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG, 2015) report by United Nations, the year 2030 is set as timeframe to achieve all of the goals in an attempt to reduce global poverty. In order to achieve these goals especially on eradication of poverty, vocational training has been cited as one of the key options that can help in creation of employment opportunities thus improving economic status of individuals. Under the economic vision and strategy in Kenya vision 2030, vocational training related to agricultural field is emphasized as one of the key factor in improving the economy. The same is mentioned by Kenya Institute for Public Policy Research and Analysis (KIPPRA, 2013) in their economic report for the year 2013 on unemployment, where they emphasized on vocational training as one way to create more employment opportunities.

Therefore, poor selection of vocational careers is caused by some factors that influence learners in vocational institutions to underrate its importance in the job market. The analysis of these factors which include social factors may reveal the way forward on how to improve vocational career choices in technical institutions. Some of

the social factors discussed in this study include the influence from parents, gender, relatives and friends. In this respect, this study analyzed social factors influencing vocational career choices made by students in technical institutions sponsored by the Catholic Church in Kenya with a special focus on the Diocese of Nakuru.

1.2 Research Question

The study was guided by the following research question:

How do social factors influence vocational career choices in technical institutions sponsored by the Catholic Diocese of Nakuru?

2. Literature Review

The study reviewed theories and past empirical studies in relation to social factors and vocational career choices.

2.1 Krumboltz's Social Learning Theory

The social learning theory was proposed by Krumboltz's in 1979. The theory which is hinged on career decision making states that learning takes place through observations as well as through direct experiences. Krumboltz mentions four factors that influence the process of career development which are genetic endowment and special abilities, environmental conditions and event, learning experiences and task approach skills.

Concerning genetic endowments and special abilities the theory explains that it is inherited qualities from parents that may set limits on individual career opportunities. It means that an individual interest may be as a result of traits and not only from one of the parents but could be traced to other members of the family. This theory takes explains the social factors that influence students career choices.

Connecting the definition of the theory about learning taking place through observation as well as learning experiences to the investigation, it perfectly aligns itself to the conditions within the long academic duration a student takes during learning a particular vocational skill in an institution. A lot goes on before a student graduates with a skill which means that during the learning process what a student goes through will affect the outcome of what the student will do both in exams and success in the chosen career. Therefore, according to this theory, the moderating factors are the ones that take place during the learning process and independent factors are the social and other factors, while the dependent factors are the outcomes of the learners' achievement.

The theory, however, does not take care about the risk of technological dependency to which society is exposed. There is more innovation coming up in different vocational fields and vocational training is continually exposed to new information technology when dealing with computer wares. The theory does not take into account individuals with learning challenges but assumes that all are very normal. The theory is the best for this study because it extensively covers key factors involved in the investigation that are carefully intertwined; as they affect an individual at different levels within the environment. To start with, the students will only select courses that they feel have high job opportunity (Abbasi & Sarwat, 2014). In addition to support this fact, Salami & Salami (2013) argue that opportunities that present themselves to the student environment play a bigger role in shaping career choice, which agrees with the environmental factor. In both ways for this research, students must have had an experience by witnessing their relatives, or family friends or read from media about certain jobs and how they trend in the society.

In relation to Krumboltz theory and learning experiences within an institution, a research on TVET institutions by Simiyu (2009) examines what goes on in an institution is determined by the style of administration and the teaching staff. According to Simiyu the administration system affects the coordination of activities both academic and non-academic in terms of implementation. Therefore, if the teachers are motivated then learning experiences of the learners becomes very beneficial thus changing their attitude to be very positive towards the chosen career.

2.2 Social Cognitive Career Theory

Social cognitive career theory comes from Albert Bandura's social cognitive theory according to Lent, Brown and Hackett (2000). This theory embeds culture, genetic endowment, gender and unexpected life events into a social context within an environment. The theory explains how certain cognitive variables like self-efficacy, outcome expectations and goals can interact with other aspects of a person such as gender, ethnicity, social support and barriers.

In addition to the theory, Lent et al (2000) in social cognitive career theory mentions three segments interlocking in the process of career development. They include development of academic and vocational interest, how individuals make educational and career choices, and third is educational and career performance and stability. In this theory, it distinguishes between choices of activities to pursue and the level of accomplishment one expect to achieve. Therefore, Lent et al (2000) argues that interest, choice and performance go hand in hand in the development of vocational career choice.

For instance, in this study due to ethnicity, a student from nomadic background will find it very unique to pick a vocational career course related to horticultural farming due to the background environment. The same would apply to a person coming from lake regions or the ocean where there is a lot of marine related activities, would simply go for vocational career befitting to such kind of an environment.

2.3 Social Factors that Influence Vocational Career Choices in Technical Institutions

2.3.1 Parents

There are different ways in which parents can affect or influence their children when it comes to career choices. To start with, Dede (2015) points out in her study on factors that inform students' choice of study and career in Ghana that; the manner in which a child is brought up creates the foundation of one of the key factors that influences a child's decisions in the future. She stresses on the modern causes of stress in life to most families covering areas in technological advancement, political, economic and industrial and education among others that forces parents to go out of their way of parenting in order to fend for their children. This type of diversion of attention from children happens unnoticed to the parents who, believes that they are doing their best to build their future. The main issue here is the parents' absence which creates lack of focus on the child's development and interest during the early years. Therefore, children end up growing without parents noticing their areas of interest, gifts and skills that they are talented in.

What's in a name counts a lot to both children and parents especially if an attitude is applied on it. In this case, parents are greatly accountable on how they introduce different professions in their families. Jungen (2008) argues that parents start influencing career decisions as soon as their children start to pronounce their job titles. This includes pilot, engineer, teacher, drivers, doctors, nurse among others. The not common ones like carpenter, mechanic, electrician, and plumber in TVET field are not famous or identifications with. The issue is on the weight given on the job title the parent holds. If the parent stresses his or her profession to be more important than the others, then that is exactly how the child is going to pick it. On the other hand, the manner in which the parent portrays other professions whether positive or negative will affects the child's imagination on that particular career. Kniveton (2004) did a research, whose findings agree with Jungen (2008) that parents influence is greater on their children's choice of career while it is maintained that family, school, community, social and economic factors plays a great role in influencing career choice.

The manner and attitude in which a parent describes other Job occupation to their children also has a lot of influence, Noshina et al (2014). The parental description is

influenced by exposure, experience, job market both locally and international levels and the requirements in terms of qualifications for the career in mind. Adding another aspect to this area, children's financial dependency on parents is a main factor that influences career choice. This makes sense especially when a parent cannot afford to educate or train a child in a certain profession due to its costly needs. Sometimes availability of scholarship may help but this is not always a guarantee to all looking for such opportunity. It is stated that close supervision, confidence and trust that parents give their children could create a lot of impact in their career choice. Trust helps to build their self-esteem and gives them courage to make choices.

Parents influence to their children in career selection can also be as a result of their approval or disapproval at economic level. Noshina et al (2014) brings in the idea that income which, parents earn in their different professions affects their attitude on how they talk about different careers to their children thus influencing their decision-making process. Approval or disapproval of a career in this case is affected by how much a person can earn from it. In this regard, if a parent looks down upon a particular vocational training course and talks negatively about it, the child will definitely be afraid to take such a course, the opposite could certainly be a possibility should a parent approves a course on monetary terms based on this argument.

Utting (2007) argues that expectations from parents can sometimes put a lot of pressure on the children hence; parents should handle their children with care. He argues that what young people think may not necessarily be what their parents think they are thinking. He emphasizes on parents to take open and participative communication with their children rather than to pressurize them to meet their expectations in career choices. Therefore, a balanced approach is very necessary which will take care of parent's concerns, the child's interest and harmonizes it with the real situation in the world of job market.

In Nigeria, Olaosebikan et al (2014) noted the fear parents have for their children not to choose jobs that will lead them to a dead end in terms of economic income. It is this fear that forces them to feel like intervening, when it comes to career choice for their children. However, this fear can be alleviated by parental closeness to a child during career exploration which leads to career maturity. It is further held that there is a positive correlation between close parental emotional attachments with career maturity. This therefore justifies that the direction the influence of vocational choice takes, still heavily depends on parental ambitions. However, concerns raised from parents are not the same as pressure coming from parents. Concerns can be viewed positively just to make sure that the child picks something beneficial for the future, but pressure on the

child to do certain coursework can result to rejection, poor performance, dissatisfaction, frustration and serious miss-match in the job market.

2.3.2 Gender Influence

In Kenya, gender sensitivity is still being experienced in many working places and this will depend with the type of job at hand. According to the Kenya National Library Services (KNLS) staff gender audit revealed more men in employment than women. In details, men in senior management were 57% while women were 43%, in middle level management men were 60% while women were 40% and in lower management level men were 52% while women were 48%. The society expectation is that certain jobs are meant for particular gender like motor vehicle mechanics will be for men and salons for women. But this is no longer the case today as the society changes and one finds women doing very well in fields associated to men only, while the same applies to men doing well in fields dominated by women only.

In a study done by Mckeen and Bu (1998), there was discussion about two factors affecting vocational choices but based on gender differences among college students namely; first is sex roles in our society which distinguishes between men and women duties, in this research men could be attributed to vocational courses like mechanics, building and construction more than dress making or knitting which looks more feminine. Second is prejudice and discrimination which affects the status of women in the society. It is indicated that enrolment data from TVET institutions show that women comprise of 30% of the total enrolment but only 5% of the 30% are in vocational area such as engineering and building and construction to name a few. The remaining 25% enroll in women traditional courses such as secretarial, nursing, and hospitalities.

Familial responsibilities among females like mother-hood due to maternity leaves together with other gender based constraints influences the opportunity structure and career choice decisions of females, Chow (2012). In addition, Chow explains that females place greater emphasis on working conditions that would suit their roles in the society which are family oriented. In the United States, it is noted that most lucrative positions in major industries are dominated by men as compared to women, that is 3% out of 500 sampled Chief Executive Officers (CEO) were women of industrial companies. In our world, today it is not necessary as to which career each gender should take and for what purpose. The focus should be on how best student can archive in a particular vocational career course and apply it to the job market outside. What institutions do to promote gender equality in providing opportunities for both sexes are key in this investigation as one of the main social effects is vocational career

guidance. There is a great need to promote more vocational career courses equally to both genders instead of treating courses with bias in terms of gender

2.3.3 Education

Education is the key to development all over the world today and this has been evidence in many United Nation Conventions which have taken place at intervals in different cities. Looking at the final report on World Education Forum (UNESCO, 2015), under the education for sustainable development there is more emphasis on developing lifelong skills. The UNESCO researchers did a lot of survey in the developing world before coming up with this report and for them to emphasize on skill development in education, shows how vocational career development is vital to many countries. There is still a lot that needs to be done in promoting vocational careers in order for us to achieve the UNESCO education agenda of 2030. The vocational careers have to be repackaged in order to attract young people who are the main target.

Kenya National Examination Council (KNEC, 2014) career guide gives all the qualifications a candidate needs to take a particular vocational course and at a particular level. This official guide presented by the government of Kenya and is used in all middle level colleges and vocational institutions in Kenya. Subject combinations are also taken care of in terms of lowest grade required for each combination allowed for a particular vocational training.

In a different study by Ndiga (2004) found out that the emphasis on academic grades to join Universities as a major factor has overshadowed focus on technical subjects. She cites Universities as institutions that mostly dwell in professional careers leading to white collar jobs which are more attractive as compared to technical educational institutions like polytechnics. Therefore, Universities should also introduce technical education subjects at higher level in order to encourage learners to specialize in them. The absence of most of the technical subjects at university level makes it difficult for a person to progress from college level hence, making the course to appear inferior only available at certificate level.

A study on vocationalization of secondary schools in Kenya by Mwiria, (2002), found out that most well performing schools avoided teaching vocational subjects due to their intensive syllabus requirements which took so long to complete. Hence, they concentrated on the common subjects and the final mean grade achievement for University entry. This kind of act diverted attention from student hence, focusing only on common examinable subjects thus neglecting practical subjects which forms the basis of vocational careers. As long as students are not exposed to practical subjects,

they will lack the motivation to venture in them in future even if they had talents in some of them.

There are four main factors that influence career choice in vocational subjects in schools according to Mwiria (2002), namely; the choice of school a student is enrolled and what is available in that school which is limited. Second is the association of vocational subject to weaker students academically, hence vocational courses are viewed as a substitute to those who cannot perform. Third is the cultural mentality. For instance, pastoral parents would view non-pastoral careers like carpentry, metal and power mechanic not suitable for their children. While fourth is the high rate of unemployment experienced by school leavers after both form four levels and college levels. Therefore, there should be a different approach in repackaging vocational subjects so as not to be seen as only meant for the weaker students. It is total misconception to think that vocational careers can never lead to well-paying jobs, hence, students should not take them, yet the economy cannot thrive without the vocational industry. The backbone of manufacturing industries is purely based on skill technology.

In a study conducted in Ghana, at the University of Cape Coast, revealed that high school teachers are the most influential to students before they join higher institutions of learning Bossman (2014). From the study, high school teachers' frequent interaction with students creates early influence in terms of career exposure. At this stage students are teenagers and tend to see most of their teachers as their role model thus takes seriously their advices. In Nigeria, it is asserted that student career is influenced by the results they get in their 12th grade despite what their interest is. The exam result dictates the next level of specialization depending on how the subjects have been performed especially in vocational field.

Among other educational factors in career choice, level of education of an individual influence on reasoning capacity. This idea is supported by Kochung and Migunde (2011), who asserts that students face difficulties in marching their abilities at their different levels to the career of their choice due to their school performance. In their research done in Kenya among form four students just about to sit for National Examinations, they found that availability of advancement opportunities and opportunities to apply skills as the most influential factors in career choice. They also cite that most of the students lacked vital information concerning different vocational courses by the time they are choosing careers before they sit for their form four exams. This same idea is advanced by Mwangi, Gongera and Thinguri (2013), in a study in Kajiado North District on career selection. They discovered that lack of career masters

in the sampled schools contributed to students' lack of knowledge in choosing what suits them best in their studies.

There is serious lack of vocational career discussion at high school level which is the right place to introduce the importance of vocational careers through practical subjects. Therefore, most institutions do not have sessions with parents whereby importance of different vocational training can be explored. Instead, most students pick their careers choices at home and proceed to the institutions with their mind already made up. Therefore, there is a great need to come up with different creative ways of encouraging vocational career courses at all levels.

2.4 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework that guided this study was adapted from Krumboltz's theory of social learning. The framework is as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

As illustrated in Figure 1, the social factors constitute the independent (predictor) variable while the dependent variable comprises of vocational career choices. The variables have been operationalized as indicated. It was presumed that the stated social factors influenced the indicated vocational career choices amongst technical institutions sponsored by the Catholic Diocese of Nakuru.

3. Material and Methods

This section outlines and explains the procedure followed to conduct the research study. It encapsulates the research design, target population, sample and sampling procedures, data collection instruments, validity and reliability, data collection procedures, and data analysis procedures.

3.1 Research Design

In this study, a mixed method approach was used, specifically, the convergent parallel mixed method design. According to Creswell (2014), this approach combines both qualitative and quantitative methods concurrently, prioritizing both methods equally. Qualitative approach relies on text and image data with the focus of gaining insights and familiarity from the respondents (Cresswell, 2014). Quantitative approach provides numeric description of trends, attitudes, or opinions of a population by studying a sample of that population (Cresswell, 2014). In this study, the quantitative and qualitative methods complemented each other and provided for triangulation of findings, hence, greater validity of emerging inferences.

3.2 Target Population

Target population is all items under consideration with similar characteristics in any field of inquiry (Kothari, 2008). The 15 Catholic-sponsored technical institutions hold vital information relevant to this study. According to Kothari (2004), target population describes the population to which the study findings are to be generalized. The members of this population share similar characteristics. For this study, the target population comprised of faculty members and students of Catholic-sponsored TVET institutions in Nakuru town. The total number included four principals, 98 faculty members and 1,514 students drawn from the aforesaid technical institutions.

3.2 Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

Sampling is a definite plan to obtain a sample or part of a population (Kothari, 2008). In this study, the technique used was purposive sampling and stratified random sampling. Purposive sampling is when a researcher selects individuals who will best help in understanding the research problem and research questions (Creswell, 2004). In this respect, stratified sampling is when specific characteristics of individuals are represented in the sample and the sample represents the true proportion in the population of individuals with certain characteristics (Creswell, 2004). For this study, Yamane's (1967) formula was used as illustrated to sample teachers and faculty members.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where n , N , and e represent sample size, study population, and error margin (5%) respectively. The error margin is equivalent to 95% confidence level.

The Yamane's equation was substituted as follows:

$$n = \frac{98}{1+98 \times 0.05^2}$$

$$n = 78.7$$

$$n = 79 \text{ teachers}$$

Therefore, from each institution, the number of teachers was distributed proportionate to their number in within the institution. The Yamane's equation was further substituted as follows to determine the sample of students.

$$n = \frac{1514}{1+1514 \times 0.05^2}$$

$$n = 316.4$$

$$n = 317 \text{ respondents}$$

The distribution from each institution in respect of faculty (79) and students (317) was done proportionately according to their numbers within each institution.

3.4 Data Collection Instruments

Data collection instruments are measuring devices used to collect information in a research study. In this study, the measuring devices used included interview guides and questionnaires. Interview guide involves presentation of oral verbal stimuli and reply in terms of oral verbal responses while, document analysis is studying facts from past institutional records and questionnaires consists of a number of questions printed or typed on a form or set of forms (Kothari, 2004). Interview guides were employed to collect qualitative data from principals and faculty members working with Catholic-sponsored TVETs while questionnaires were used to facilitate collection of data from students of the aforementioned institutions.

3.5 Pilot, Validity and Reliability Tests

The researcher selected some students from independent technical institutions, which are not among the ones selected for the study but offer similar vocational courses. According to Kothari (2004), the number of participant in a pilot study constitutes 10% of the total participant in the study. In this study there were 317 participants, hence, the required percentage was calculated to be 32 students. The quantitative measuring instruments were administered to the selected students and data recorded

independently. Both the teachers and the principal were not among the ones selected to participate in the study.

For content validity in this study, the researcher involved three other teachers in the field of vocational training from different institutions to independently verify that the content of the measuring instruments really focused on the intended research question. The teachers worked to verify that questions and interviews covered social factors influencing vocational career choices.

For qualitative data analysis, the themes gathered and recorded during the pilot test were used in comparison to the ones that came out in the real test for the study from the selected institutions. The reliability of the instruments was portrayed by how similar or different the themes were both from the pilot test results in comparison to the real test results. The quantitative data as captured with the facilitation of the research questionnaire and collected during the pilot study was subjected to reliability testing using half-split method. The method involved randomly separating the data collected from the 32 respondents into a set of two batches (Batch A and Batch B) each constituting a set of 16 questionnaires. The data pertinent to the study variables were then correlated against each other using Pearson’s correlation coefficient. The reliability test results are as illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1: Results of Reliability Test

		Batch B
Batch A	Pearson Correlation	.644**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	32

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As indicated in Table 1, there was a positive, strong and statistically significant correlation between the data collected using Batch A and Batch B of the questionnaires used ($r = 0.644$; $p < 0.05$). The stronger the correlation, the greater the reliability of the data collection tool, and the reverse was equally true. Against this backdrop, therefore, the strong and significant correlation depicted in Table 6, implied that the research instrument was overall reliable for use in the collection of data for the main study.

3.6 Data Collection Procedure

According to Cresswell (2014) data collection procedures means setting structured steps and boundaries to be followed in the data collection. The researcher first obtained clearance letter from Catholic University of Eastern Africa, Department of Post

Graduate Studies in Education. The researcher then proceeded to the National Council for Science Technology and Innovation (NACOSTI) for research permit. The researcher went to the County Director of Education's office where the selected institutions are located to inform the Education authorities of the intended study, then visited the selected institutions and got acquainted with the relevant authorities such as the Principals and Head of Departments to explain to them the purpose of the study. The researcher distributed and collected the questionnaires through the Head of Departments of the selected institutions and conducted interviews with the selected participants.

3.7 Data Analysis Procedure

Data analysis procedure means the steps followed to make sense out of the image data (Cresswell, 2014). In this study, both qualitative and quantitative data were analyzed concurrently keeping both results independently before interpretation and relating how they conformed to each other. Quantitative data base of responses was created then coded before it was entered into SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 24. The tools in this software were used to perform different statistical analyses like creating variables, subsets, replacing missing values among others depending on the answers given by the participants. Using the tools of SPSS there were operations like addition, subtraction, division and multiplication of variables to create new variables in order to obtain frequencies, percentages and mean scores. The results were produced in tables following the order of variables picked and created from the questionnaires under different sections guided by the research questions.

For qualitative data for both the principals and the teachers, the researcher organized emerging responses into different themes based on the structured questions during the interviews. In order to avoid getting out of topic during the interviews and during analysis, reference was always made to the original research questions of the study so that focus is maintained. After both results have been analyzed independently, the researcher interpreted both results by mixing the main corresponding ideas to make meaning out of the findings in accordance to the research question.

4. Results and Discussions

This section presents the results of the data analyses. The first part outlines the response rate. This is followed by results and discussions pertinent to social factors and vocational career choices.

4.1 Response Rate

Response rate is defined as the proportion of the number of respondents who participate in a given study against the number of targeted respondents (Nulty, 2008). In this study as shown in Table 2, there was a total of 400 targeted respondents across the selected TVETs. These include 4 principals, 79 teachers, and 317 students.

Table 2 : Response Rate

	Principals	Teachers	Students	Aggregated Sum
Total Respondents	4	79	317	400
Participated Respondents	4	63	225	292
Response Rate (%)	100.00	79.75	70.98	73.00

It was observed as shown in Table 2 that a total of 4 principals, 63 teachers, and 225 students resulting in an aggregate sum of 400 participated in the study. This translated to 100.00%, 79.75%, and 70.98% response rate for principals, teachers and students respectively. The aggregate response rate was thus established to be 73.00% which according to Nulty (2008) was deemed sufficient.

4.2 Social Factors Influencing Vocational Career Choices

Under social factors influencing vocational career choices, the study focused on what influenced the students to learn about their institutions, their previous working experiences, influence from their relatives and friends who trained in the same course, and how they and their friends perceive their courses in terms of difficulty, marketability and the changing world.

4.2.1 Sources of Information about their Institutions

The study sought to find out how students came to know about their institutions from their social circles. It is evident that certain forces must have influenced them which could range from family, friends, social media and other factors that could depend on how exposed they were.

Table 3: Distribution of students by how they learnt about their institutions

Sources of information about institutions	Frequency	Percentage
High school principal	1	.4
Google	1	.4
Media adverts	17	7.6
Friends and family	206	91.6
Total	225	100.0

As shown in Table 3, majority of students who are enrolled in TVET institution obtained information regarding their present institutions through family and friends (91.6%). Very few students obtained information of their current institutions from heads of their Secondary Schools (0.4%), and from online sites such as Google search (0.4%).

The data further revealed that 7.6% obtained information from media advertisements. The findings in Table 3 reveal that most students rely heavily on the very immediate persons in their lives to get reliable information. This is a clear indication of how much influence such people have on them and how much affect their choices in life. These findings agree with Noshina et al (2014), that parent’s way of describing a job influences a child perception about the job. Regarding parental influence, it is argued that at adolescent stage is where the youth’s mind can be influenced most as they are still living their parent’s dreams.

Another interpretation from the Principals could be that most institutions do not advertise online. *“We usually advertise by distributing our brochures to various Churches, shopping centres, youth seminars and occasionally in the Radio.”* This could also be an indication that most TVET institution still makes more use of print media such as brochures or magazines and newspapers. But from the teachers’ opinion, most institutions using brochures and paying a lot to get slots in magazines and newspapers are business oriented. The findings of family and friends at 91.6% could mean that the influence is associated to someone who knows the institution very well and the success of its graduates in the job market. Hence, it means that referrals of institutions and courses to take by people known to the students have greater influence.

4.2.2 Distribution of Students by Previous Working Experience

Students in TVET institutions are in the employment age legally, hence, there could be high chances of some of them to have been involved in different employment fields before joining the institutions. Even though the main purpose of the institution is to prepare them for employment, their previous knowledge and experience could have an impact in their attitude thus affecting their selection.

Table 4: Distribution of students by previous working experience

Students with working experience	Frequency	Percentage
Family business	31	13.8
Self-employed	13	5.8
Employed	56	24.9
Never	125	55.6
Total	225	100.0

Table 4 shows distribution in deferent perspective regarding student's work experience before they joined their current institution of learning. Most of the students in TVET institutions had no work experience (55.6%), however, 24.9% were in formal employment before their enrolment to technical institutions. It was also observed that 13.8% were in family businesses while a merely 5.8% had already tried self-employment.

The findings that majority of students did not have working experience in Table 12, concurs with the study done by Mwangi et al (2013), in Kajiado North District on career selection where students were found to be ill prepared in the field of Vocational career selection. Students in high school were found to mainly focus on joining Universities after their KCSE exams." This was an observation from the faculty. The idea of working and employment does not feature to them as a possibility immediately after high school. From the Principal's views, students were seen to have very high ambitions after school such that Vocational careers only came as a second thought. Therefore, it can be observed from these findings that very few students from the categories of family business, self-employed and employed especially in the field of Vocational skills, had an idea of vocational career they wanted to do. The bigger population falling in the category of never in the table had no any exposure to vocational career, thus met these careers for the first time in technical institutions.

For those who had previous working experience either in formal or self-employment or were involved in family business, could have joined TVET institutions, with the intention to advance in their areas of interest. For this category of students, the theory of work adjustment can be applied to them in the sense that, their interest resulting from their environment led to their selection of the career that they are pursuing.

From the interviews with faculty members, it was observed that those who were self-employed or engaged in already family business excelled well in the areas of their interest due to the experience they have gained. Students did well when their interests were complimented by their passion in their choice of vocational careers. This observation was very common among those students who were self-employed. According to the faculty members, they only needed managerial skills which could be gained from offering entrepreneurship courses to help them run their businesses.

4.2.3 The influence by Relatives and Friends

One of the greatest influence in our social life is the people we are living with. Social cognitive career theory by Albert Bandura touches on influences related to genetic endowment, cultural and life events in the social context. In this study, students were

asked questions regarding the influence they get from the experiences of their friends and relatives who have done the same career courses that they were currently training on.

Table 5: Distribution of Students by Relatives and Friends Trained in Same Course

Students with relatives trained in same course they are taking	Frequency	Percentage
No	111	49.3
Yes	114	50.7
Total	225	100.0

The results in Table 5 show that 50.7% of the sampled students admitted that there were either friends or family members or both who had trained in related courses they are taking. On the other hand, 49.3% of the students disputed that they had friends or family members who had pursued the same course as them.

From these results, it can be interpreted that as family and friends influence students in TVET institutions there is still a large number (49.3%) who make choices according to their own personal interest. For those who had relatives and friends trained in the same field as they are training, their choice could have been attributed to how they have observed the success of their mentors. The focus on the social context at this level was on the relationship the students had that might have influenced their decisions. Therefore, it can be interpreted from table 13 that, despite the influence of relatives and friends' success in a vocational career, individual students could still select different vocational career as per their personal interest.

Teachers observed that, most of the new students changed their courses within the first semester after they have discovered what they really want. This observation clearly supports the lack of exposure from the 49.1% who responded not to have been influenced by relatives and friends before they came to the institution. The Principal's had a view that influence from relative and friends only come when they are successful in their vocational careers but when the opposite happens then they will develop negative attitude towards the course.

4.2.4 Perception of the Course by other Students in terms of Marketability, Difficulty and the Changing World

The understanding of vocational careers can be influenced by the image of the career itself as it is perceived by other people. In this case, the focus was more at business level especially on the marketability and difficulty in technicality involved in a particular vocational career in relation to the technological advancement in the changing world

Table 6: Perception of course by other students in terms of marketability, difficulty and the changing world

Students' perception of courses	Frequency	Percentage
Does not appeal to many but marketable	86	38.2
Very difficult but marketable	139	61.8
Total	225	100.0

According to the findings on Table 6, majority of the students (61.8%) perceived the courses they were pursuing as being very difficult but also marketable. The key factor here for them was the marketability of the course as compared to the difficulty. They maintained their focus to employment possibility and business opportunities after doing the course due to its marketability. Meanwhile, 38.2% were of the view that the course they were pursuing failed to appeal to many people but were also marketable.

Given that all students admitted that the courses offered by TVET institutions were marketable, then it implies that the marketability of the courses offered by these education institutions was the most crucial factor that made students to enroll with them. These findings can be related to Abbas and Sarwat (2014) argument, that students will only select courses with high job opportunity.

From the interview conducted on faculty members, it was observed that students were employed faster in the service industries as compared to the production industries. In this case, service industry courses were mainly marketable but did not appeal to many students such as hotel waiters, hair designers, computer applications, painting among others. Meanwhile production courses were difficult but marketable with high returns such as masonry, carpentry, fashion and design and plumbing. They agreed with the idea of marketability but added that superiority and gender also played a role. Since investing in career chosen is expensive and irreversible (Boosman, 2013) considerations such as capacity, opportunity, values, limitations and focus on real world should be made. The Principals added their observation by saying that marketability of a course depends on the prevailing economy as it keeps on changing due varying needs within our environment.

4.3 Vocational Career Choices in TVET Institutions

When career promotion is done in high schools especially at form two level where subject selection takes place, the focus mainly is geared to University degree courses. But as time goes by, the reality of the matter comes after form four results when some students are referred to technical institutions because they did not qualify for

University placement. This is why TVET courses also need to be promoted at early stages so that they are not taken as second class to University degree courses.

4.3.1 Vocational Career Courses

From the document analysis of this study, it was observed that there is still great need for promotion of vocational careers in order to increase more opportunities for employment for TVET graduates in the job market. The Principal's observed that "Enrollment in TVET institutions is higher during the month of February after form four results are announced and goes down in the month of August when Universities opens." This could be interpreted that some students only enroll to TVET institutions for short courses as they wait for their university intake time to come. In as much as it is a positive move to learn some skills before joining university, this should be encouraged even at University level during their on-going degree courses as the future is always uncertain. From the teacher's interview, they also observed that "Students who take short TVET courses don't enroll for any exams but only do them for the purpose of gaining some skills." They also observed that computer applications take the lead in this area.

Figure 2: Analysis of examination enrollment of some vocational careers
 (Adapted from Comboni College in Nakuru)

The chart shows Electrical Installation having the highest number of enrollment for National Examination then followed by Mechanics. Carpentry takes the lowest enrollment while Painting, tailoring, Building and Construction are almost at the same level although they vary slightly. There are many students who take Vocational careers but this chart only shows a representation of those who go to the level of enrolling for

Examination with recognized bodies like National Industrial Training Authority (NITA) and Kenyan National Examination Council (KNEC)

According to the college principals, it was observed that, taking exams with registered bodies in vocational careers enabled students to move to higher levels of specialization. This explained the need to encourage students to get certificates in some areas for the purpose of progressiveness. Advancing from one stage to another by itself is a motivating factor to the students and helps to build self-esteem of an individual.

Moreover, before any group graduates, the teachers observed that *“there is lack of entrepreneurship workshops to empower the graduates with necessary skills before joining the employment world.”* It was also observed that TVET institutions have not taken major steps to introduce courses that had the capacity to merge skills from more than one department in order to maximize employment opportunities. This window of creativity is already allowed by TIVETA (2013) board to technical institutions as long as they are approved by the board. This is the area that has not been fully explored regarding the changing economic times.

5. Recommendations

In view of social aspects influencing Vocational Career Choices, the Kenyan Institute of Curriculum Development (KICD) should come up with programs at secondary school level especially from form one, that can promote not only university courses after KCSE but also combine with TVET related courses since not all students go to Universities. There should be a strong link between high schools and TVET institution in order to create awareness of vocational careers. TVET courses are as important as any other and are very high paying depending on how they are handled.

TVET institution’s administrators should team up with universities to tailor make courses that can progress from lower levels to higher levels through TVETA. This could be a great motivating factor to those who think that vocational career courses just end up at tertiary level. TVET institutions should come up with well-coordinated promotion teams or career guiding departments and educate youths on the importance of vocational careers in the modern job market. From this study, it is clear that family and friends have the greatest influence, however, there is great danger in leaving career information to family and friends because this kind of influence heavily depends on what is trending but does not take care of future possibilities. TVET institutions should also embrace technology such as social media when advertising and inculcate information technology in all courses offered in order to make their students techno-savvy graduates.

Institutions should come up with guiding policies on how to help and streamline student's choices on vocational careers. Institution guiding policies will help students to solve the problem of miss-match in terms of skills required in the job market, in the employment field which is created by technological development. This study is in line with Kenya Vision 2030 in finding the way forward for economic poverty eradication by promoting vocational career courses.

6. Conclusions

The study concluded that TVET institutions target mostly school leavers especially those who have finished KCSE level. Most of these students were already exposed to career knowledge in high school but TVET careers were never emphasized. Therefore, their family and friends have played a great role in influencing them to take the courses they are pursuing in TVET institutions. It can also be concluded that employment is the major concern and focus that motivate TVET students to undertake the courses.

It was also inferred that, vocational careers offered in TVET institutions are still very relevant to our current economy. Based on this study, most TVET institutions have maintained their focus on traditional vocational courses without using much the window of creativity offered by TIVETA. The current vocational programs are very good but they need upgrading in line with the changing economic times. There is a lot of opportunity for expansion of TVET courses in the current employment market, if creativity on modern technology is maximized. Maximization can happen by fully utilizing local resources and involving all stake holders involved in the field of TVET education.

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